

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B141
Date: 19 Nov 2005
Take Off 11:06:21
Landing: 16:04:46
Flight Time 4h58m29

Campaign: Cirrus
Operating Area: Irish Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	3 rd Pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
6	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
7	Dropsondes/ CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	MARRS/DEMOS	Ian Rule	Met Office
10	MARRS/DEMOS Training	James Bowles	Met Office
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
12	SWS	Martin Glew	Met Office
13	ADA / CPI	Ian Crawford	Manchester University
14	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Taylor	Met Office
15	TAFTS	Jon Murray	Imperial College London
16	Satellite Applications	Brett Candy	Met Office
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B141 Track 19-NOV-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B141
 Date: 19 Nov 2005
 Project: Cirrus
 Location: Irish Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
084557		Position	-.37 kft	359	50'43.93N,3'24.81W
102134		De-Ice	-.38 kft	100	Wings and tail
103921		INU	-.38 kft	100	To Navigate
110621		T/O	1.3 kft	324	Exeter
111112		ASPs	5.9 kft	331	Open
113038		Videos	10.0 kft	316	Start UFC & DFC
113237	114732	Profile 1	10.0 - 0.04 kft	309	500fpm 5k' Q1031
114949	115016	Profile 1	0.00 - -.25 kft	144	500'-250', Q1030
115017	120130	Run 1	-.25 - -.26 kft	143	
115258		Heimann	-.25 kft	137	Cal SST=12.6C
120141	120904	Profile 2	-.22 - 5.0 kft	134	500fpm to FL50
121242	122253	Profile 2	5.0 - 14.0 kft	304	
122329	122928	Profile 2	14.0 - 19.9 kft	023	
123048	123202	Profile 2	20.0 - 21.0 kft	042	
123504	124438	Profile 2	21.0 - 29.0 kft	042	
125341	130233	Run 2	29.1 - 29.0 kft	152	
130654		Videos	29.0 kft	324	Change tapes
130801	131001	Orbit	29.1 - 29.0 kft	357	45deg right, 360
131107	131256	Orbit 2	29.0 kft	087	45deg right, 080
131535	132333	Profile 3	29.1 - 33.1 kft	320	500fpm abv FL311
132407		Event	33.0 kft	331	Contraailing
132938	133331	Profile 3	33.0 - 34.0 kft	172	
133515	133731	Profile 3	34.0 - 35.0 kft	119	
134031	135049	Run 3.1	35.1 - 35.0 kft	318	
134233		Sonde	35.0 kft	312	Launch #01
134828		Sonde	35.0 kft	314	Launch #02, on RFC
135338	140348	Run 3.2	35.0 kft	148	Still contraailing
140648	140819	Profile 4	35.1 - 34.0 kft	326	
140819	141830	Run 4	34.0 kft	318	
141351		Videos	34.1 kft	317	Change tapes
142141	142406	Profile 5	34.1 - 32.0 kft	137	
142406	143001	Run 5	32.0 kft	136	In Cloud
143452	143715	Profile 6	32.1 - 30.0 kft	312	
143716	144605	Run 6	30.0 kft	311	Still contraailing
144859	145144	Profile 7	30.0 - 28.0 kft	152	
145145	145835	Run 7.1	28.0 kft	139	
150258	151043	Run 7.2	28.0 kft	320	Not contraailing
151121	151246	Orbit 3	28.1 kft	025	50deg right, 010
151358	151525	Orbit 4	28.1 - 28.0 kft	076	50 deg right, 060
151718	152150	Profile 8	28.0 - 32.0 kft	176	In Cirrus
152150	153803	Run 8	32.0 kft	185	
152500		Videos	32.0 kft	190	End tapes
154632		ASPs	18.6 kft	165	Closed
160446		Land	-.38 kft	174	Exeter
160939		Position	-.38 kft	107	50'43.93N,3'24.81W

B141 Track 19-NOV-05

CAESAR SORTIE BRIEF (updated 18/11/05)
Measurement of cirrus multi-frequency radiative properties

B141 – 19th November 2005

Aim

The aim is to study the radiative properties at multiple frequencies of cirrus over the sea, coincident with an overpass of the CloudSat-Aqua Satellite.

Straight and level runs are to be made above, in and below the cirrus, to determine the radiative and microphysical properties. Runs should be perpendicular to the wind direction and advecting with it. Orbits are to be made below the cloud with SWS viewing upwards to determine the phase function of the ice particles.

Weather

Cirrus with clear skies below.

Operating region

Irish Sea

Clearances

Clearances will be required for flying at 100ft and for dropping sondes.

Notam area B.

Operating Area: Irish Sea

	Time	Manoeuvre	Duration (min)
1	10:35	Takeoff from Exeter & Transit at appropriate level to enter operating area at min altitude	30
2	11:05	Straight and level run of 10 mins duration at 250 ft over sea	10
3	11:15	Profile ascent from min altitude to 1000ft below cirrus base.	30
4	11:45	Fly 1 straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus, of 10 mins.	12
5	11:57	Fly two orbits below cloud at max banking angle (60 deg?) in nappy-pin manoeuvre.	10
6	12:07	Profile ascent to max altitude	10
7	12:17	Fly 3 straight and level reciprocal runs at max altitude, each of 10 mins. Drop 1 or 2 sondes.	36
8	12:35	Satellite overpass	
9	12:53	Profile descent to 1000ft below max alt (in cloud)	3
10	12:56	Fly 1 straight and level runs in cloud, of 10 mins	12
11	13:08	Profile descent to 1000ft above cirrus base	10
12	13:18	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs in cloud, each of 10 mins	24
13	13:42	Profile descent to 1000ft below cirrus base	3
14	13:45	Fly two straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft below cirrus base, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins.	24
15	14:09	Fly two orbits below cloud at max banking angle (60 deg?) in nappy-pin manoeuvre.	10
16	14:19	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cloud top or max alt.	15
17	14:34	Fly 3 straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft above cirrus top or max alt, each of 10 mins. Drop 1 sonde in 1 st run.	36
18	15:10	Profile descent to transit altitude	15
19	15:25	Transit to Exeter	30
20	15:55	Land Exeter	TOTAL 320

Requirements for ARIES and SWS

In the cloud:

ARIES: nadir with calcs every 2 minutes ideally during turns.

SWS: series of 0, 180, 90 and 45 degree viewing angles during every run with appropriate calcs (measurements to be used to test Robin Hogan's 3D stochastic model).

Above cloud:

1st run above cloud

ARIES & SWS both viewing nadir. Calibrations to be coordinated such that both instruments simultaneously view the cloud for the maximum time.

2nd run above cloud

ARIES & SWS both viewing nadir **then** for last 2 minutes both viewing zenith .

Below cloud:

ARIES & SWS both viewing zenith, including during the orbits. Calibrations to be coordinated such that both instruments simultaneously view the cloud for the maximum time.

B141 – Mission Scientist De-brief

19th Nov 2005

Dr Clare Lee

The aim of the sortie was to study cirrus using radiative and in-situ measurements. The operating area was in the Irish Sea, which limited the length of run due to air traffic corridors. Generally where the cirrus was thicker there was patchy Cu below. Contrails were being produced generally above FL300. Engine details were noted.

The takeoff time from Exeter was delayed to 11:05 due to icing of the aircraft. There was concern that some of the deicing fluid may have run over instrument inputs during the takeoff, although the instrumentation were covered during the deicing process. The delay meant that the aircraft was not in position above the cirrus during the AQUA overpass.

A profile descent (P1) was made into the Aberporth area, which had generally clear sky. To the western end of the profile the cirrus became thicker, but also small patches of Cu increased. A run (R1) was made at 250ft (limited due to the pilots) to characterise the sea surface temperature. At the SE end of the run, it became clear sky again.

An interrupted profile (P2) was made to FL290 ending further North (East of the Isle of Man), where there was cirrus. A run (R2) was made below the Ci, with ARIES and SWS viewing zenith. As the Cu patches thin below, the Ci also thinned above. At 13:08 two 45 deg right hand orbits were made in the “nappie-pin” manoeuvre. An interrupted profile (P3) was made to characterise the in-situ particles from FL290 to maximum altitude (FL350). Ice crystals were seen with 2DC and CPI, but in small concentrations (maximum 100 per litre). The cirrus extended above FL350. Two reciprocal runs were made (R3.1 & R3.2) with ARIES and SWS viewing nadir. At 13:42 drop sonde 1 was launched and 13:49 drop sonde 2.

A profile descent (P4) was made deeper into the cloud to FL340, though still only low particle concentrations. On run 4, ARIES and SWS viewed zenith. A profile descent (P5) to FL320 was made and a run (R5) at that level with ARIES and SWS viewing zenith. A profile descent (P6) was made to FL300 to get below the cloud, but particles were still being detected during run 6.

A profile descent was made to FL280, where particles were no longer being detected and contrailing also stopped. A straight and level run (7.1) was made below the cloud with large radiometers viewing zenith. A short reciprocal run (7.2) was made, followed by 2 orbits starting at 60 degrees relaxing to 50 deg to maintain altitude. A final profile (P8) was made to FL320 to be in the cloud. Run 8 was made at FL320 heading towards Exeter, coming out of the cloud at 15:35. Landing at Exeter was at 16:04, giving a sortie time of 4hr 58mins.

Summary

A moderately successful flight, cirrus was not ideal due to its inhomogeneity and inability to climb above it, as well as some low cloud below. Useful contrail data.

Instrument status

AVAPS – OK

ARIES – OK

MARSS – OK

Deimos – suspect data. High noise?

SWS – OK

Cloud Physics – OK, except PCSP and 2DP at high alt.

ADA CPI – OK

FWVS – OK

TAFTS – LW too noisy. SW zenith –OK. SW nadir – U/S.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.141**.....
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **19/11/05**.....

 Page **1**..... of **8**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:05				Exeter	T10. Delay due to icing of aircraft. Mainly clear $\frac{3}{8}$ Ci, windst.
11:31			313	52.3N 4W	Starting descent. Clear above Ci ahead.
11:32:37	P1	100	311		Profile descent. 1000ft/min.
11:38:56					Changing to 500ft/min descent.
11:41:30				52.7N 4.9W	Clear above, haze to E. $\frac{1}{8}$ Ci
11:45					Start $\frac{3}{8}$ W v. thin. profile descending underneath before reaching it.
11:47:32	Print.	500ft.			Turning around to clear area. + edge of flight boundary.
11:49:49	Print.	500ft.			
11:50:17	R1	250ft.			Small W patchy above.
11:53:19		"			Clear above. Heimann 12.6 C.
12:01:30	Rland	250ft.			Clear above Ci only in dist.
12:01:41	P1	250ft.			Profile climb.
			136		Clear above Ci in dist. bt. over land.
12:09:04	Print.	F150			Intercept. profile going over land slightly. (12:07:44)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.141**.....

 Date **19/11/05**.....

 Page **2** of **8**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:12:42	PR start		305		
12:22:53	P2int.	140ft.			Intend to turn to right.
12:23:29	P2start.		027		Cloud physics all clear sky.
12:29:28	P2int.	FL200			
12:30:68	P2start	FL200	043		
12:32:02	P2int.	FL210	042		SWS seeing signal in zenith. cloud physics nothing heading through airways to more northern area to get good Ci
					Missing Ci + Satellite coincidence.
12:35:04	P2st.	FL210	043		S.W. off to W
12:37:00		FL240	042		SWS seeing large signal. Air traffic restricting us to FL290.
12:43:32					
12:46:38	P2end	FL290			
12:53:41	R2	FL290	145	Near Isle of Man	Run below Ci SWS + AOCIES ↑
					At start of an 2D sun something, but no image
					N.B. still got 3/8 SW below.
13:00:19				53.8N 3.7W	S.W. v. small amounts SWS seeing less Ci above also.
13:02:19	R2 end.				Clear below

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.141**.....

 Date **19/11/05**.....

 Page **3** of **8**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Turning to left.
					heading towards thicker Ci
					but also st. w below.
13:07:45					Orbit to right hand.
	Ostart		360		Start orbit 45°
					clear below
13:09:32	Ostart				Possibility of catching some stw.
13:10:01	Oclear				
13:11:07	O2start		080		Orbit right ~45°.
					clear below.
13:12:21	Oclear				Some patchy w. (1/8) below.
13:12:56	Oclear				Continuing around to head
					into correct direction.
13:15:35	P3	FL290	321		→ FL350.
13:16:26		FL300			Small ice crystals ~75µm → 100µm
					CPI 100. 150µm
					v. low concs. ~50/l.
					T-52.5C, TD -48.6C
					(500ft/min climb)
					hexagonal columns in CPI
					2D seeing fewer particles.
13:23:00					peak 100/l. only.
					175µm sizes. max. not much changes.
13:23:35			320.		Contrailing.
13:23:33	P3int.	FL330			T-58.5 TD-53.23

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....*141*.....

 Date*19/11/05*.....

 Page *4* of *8*

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132649.					Contrails:
					N1 96.4, 96.4, 96.4, 96.3
					T&T 757, 738, 725, 765
					N2 90.2, 90.6, 90.0, 90.0
					FWV 5.6, 5.5, 5.6, 5.7
					FWVS:
					-48 Dew Pt.
					Taircraft = -58.69, T _D -54.06
132938	P3 stat.	FL330	172	54.4, 3.8W	Still contrails:
					N1 96.5, 96.4, 96.5, 96.4
					T&T 756.5, 737, 724.5, 763.5
					N2 90.2, 90.55, 90.0, 90.0
					T = -59.9C, T _D -54.44
					FWVS = -49C dew pt. needs
					analysing afterwards as
					small rants make it hard
					to determine FWVS dew pt.
13:33:31	P3 int.	FL340			Air traffic interruption.
13:35:15	P3 stat.	FL340	118		Recommence climb.
13:37:31.	P3 end.	FL350.			
13:40:31	R3.1	FL350.			Start Run
	S1	FL350.			Side drop.
13:45:09					2D: seeing ice again.
					10/2 75km.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.141**.....
FAAM © 2004

Date 19/11/05.....

Page 5 of 8

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:46:50.					Contrails:
					N1 96.8, 96.8, 96.9, 96.8
					TBT. 753, 741, 721, 767
					N2 90.0, 90.5, 89.85, 89.7
					FF 5.3, 5.2, 5.2, 5.3.
13:47:37		FL350	314		Seeing St. W below.
					SWS has also been seeing at large values.
~ 13:49:00	S2	FL350.		54.5 ^N , 4.2 ^W	Drop Smoke. see 2D
					Still contrailing
13:49:34.					2D low concs. → hgt. fairly large particles. CPl hexagonal but not many.
13:50:49	R3.1end	FL350		54.7 ^N , 4.5 ^W	Turning right.
13:53:38	R3.2st.		151		
14:01:51					Contrailing. still.
14:03:48	R3.2end				Turning reciprocal. left h.turn.
14:06:48	R4.1st	FL350	326	53.7 ^N 3.1 ^W	Profile descent. → FL340
14:08:19	R4.2nd	FL340			
14:08:19	R4.1st.		318		Contrails (ALBS + SWS ↑)
					N1 90.8, 90.85, 91.0
					TBT 70.1 679 668 717
					N2 87.6 87.8, 87.5, 87.5.
					FF 4.6
					2012 2DC.
					clear below.
14:16:30	R4.2nd	FL340.			End on right turn.

CPl + 2D not seeing much conc.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**...141.....

Date

 Page 6 of 8

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:21:41	P5	FL340	137		Profile descent to FL320. W 3/4 at Northern Excl. 2DC 301L.
14:24:06	P5end.	FL320	136	54.3N 37W	
"	R5				clear below contrails
					N1 88.2, 88.2, 88.1, 88.1
					W 685, 666, 655, 702
					N2 86.9, 87.0, 86.7, 86.7
					FF 4.6, 4.5, 4.5, 4.7
14:26					2D, CPl seeing larger concs. aggregated shapes.
14:27:18					conc. much less on 2D. can now also see W below.
14:30:01	R5end.				end run, left turn then right to get cont track.
14:34:32	P6				descent ⇒ FL300
14:36:					plates 300 ⇒ 400µm aggregates, columns ~75µm x 300µm
14:37:16	P6end	FL300	310		
"	R6st.				Still seeing crystals v. large 500 x 600µm in CPl
14:44:48					seeing pristine crystals + some clusters. in CPl.
14:46:05	R6end				End run, turning right.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.141**.....
FAAM © 2004

Date **19/11/05**.....

Page **7** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					N1 85.9 Contracting but less so
					TGT 668
					N2 86.0
					FF 4.4
14:48:59	P7.4	FL300	168		descent \Rightarrow FL280
14:50:36					Stopped contracting:
					N1 69.55, 69.9, 69.9, 69.5
					TGT 594, 567, 523, 569
					N2 80.2, 80.2, 78.6, 78.9
					FF 3.1, 3.0, 3.2, 3.3
14:50:59		FL280.			2D not seeing any Ci or CPl.
14:51:45	Plead	FL280			
" "	R7.4	FL280	138		Small Ci below.
14:58:35	R7.4	FL280			and on left turn. ^{then right.} v-small Ci below.
					SZA \sim 80°?
15:02:58	R7.2	FL280	313		3/8 Ci below.
15:05:00			310		2D seeing v. small ones.
					clear below.
					No contrails.
					N1 88.2, 90.7, 91.1, 89.3
					TGT 692, 702, 693, 720
					N2 87.6, 88.9, 88.8, 87.9
					FF 5.2, 5.5, 5.6, 5.5
15:10:43?	R7.2				
15:11:21	03				Orbit to right. 60° \Rightarrow 90°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** 141.....

Date 19/11/05.....

Page 8 of 8

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:12:46	O3 end	FL280			end orbit. seems 50° limit to angle.
15:13:58	O4 st.		060		
15:15:25	O4 end				End of orbit turning to continue on heading.
15:17:18	P8 st.	FL280 FL280	177		Profile climb. → FL320
15:20:29		FL280	185		Contrailing. M1 96.1, 96.1, 96.2, 96.3 T87 758, 744.5, 730, 710 M2 90.5, 90.7, 90.3, 90.3 FF 5.75, 5.7, 5.7, 5.8
15:21:50	P8 end	FL320	185		CPI conc. low size ~ 300 μm. 2D seeing ~ 3/4 concs. in profile.
15:21:50 15:32:28	R8 st.	FL320	189		
15:35:03		FL320	189	52.6N 3.9W	2D not seeing anything really at all now.
15:38:03	R8 end	FL320			end science. Inst. status. ANAPS - OK. ARIES - OK. MARSS/Demos - OK. Demos? suspect. SWS - OK. Cloud physics - OK etc. ^{PCSP} 2D at high alt. ADA-CPI - OK. FLVS - OK. TAFTS - good.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 141

Date: 19/11/05 Operator: MAP DRS time:09:28:00 DAU1 time:09:28:00 DAU2 time: 09:28:00 DAU3 time:09:28:00 AUX1 time:09:28:00 AUX2 time: Page 1 of 1

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:32:37	30	0.07	0	1												Start Profile 1 from FL100	
11:33:44	55	0.07		1												FL090	
11:34:49	55	0.08		1												FL080	
11:35:54	80	0.07		1												FL070	
11:36:58	120	0.07		1												FL060	
11:38:05	40	0.06		1												FL050	
11:39:20	30	0.06		1												FL040	
11:41:06	55	0.06		1												FL030	
11:43:26	250	0.08		10												FL020	
11:45:32	300	0.08		10												FL010	
11:50:14	360	0.08		10												End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ 250'	
11:51:00	270	0.08	1	10													
11:53:00	245	0.07		10													
11:55:00	300	0.06		10													
11:57:00	200	0.07		15													
11:59:00	250	0.06		10													
12:01:00	290	0.06		10													
12:01:35																End of Run 1	
12:01:43	290	0.06		10												Start Profile 2 from 250'	
12:03:25	60	0.06		5												FL010	
12:05:20	40	0.06		3												FL020	
12:06:24	Noise			1												FL030	
12:07:46	20	0.06		1												FL040	
12:09:05	Noise			1												FL050	
12:13:51	85	0.07		1												FL060	
12:15:10	65	0.06														FL070	
12:16:15	60	0.06														FL080	
12:17:25	35	0.06														FL090	
12:18:29	65	0.06														FL100	
12:19:37	40	0.06														FL110	
12:20:42	65	0.07														FL120	
12:21:49	45	0.07														FL130	
12:22:58	15	0.06														FL140	
12:24:36	Noise															FL150	
12:25:44	20	0.06														FL160	
12:26:39	20	0.06														FL170	
12:27:36	20	0.06														FL180	
12:28:33	10	0.06														FL190	
12:29:27	10	0.06														FL200	
12:32:01	Noise															FL210	
12:36:12	Noise															FL220	
12:37:11	Noise															FL230	
12:38:22	Noise															FL240	
12:39:35	Noise															FL250	
12:40:53	Noise															FL260	
12:42:04	Noise															FL270	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 141

Date: 19/11/05 Operator: MAP DRS time:09:28:00 DAU1 time:09:28:00 DAU2 time: 09:28:00 DAU3 time:09:28:00 AUX1 time:09:28:00 AUX2 time: Page 2 of 2

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:43:05	Noise		1					Noise								FL280	
12:44:38	Noise							Noise								End of profile 2 @ FL290	
12:46:00								Rearm 1									
12:53:41								Noise								Start Run 2 @ FL290	
12:54:00	Noise			20		3		Noise									
12:56:00	Noise							Noise									
12:58:00	Noise							Noise									
13:00:00	Noise							Noise									
13:02:00	Noise							Noise									
13:02:33								Noise								End of Run 2	
13:08:00						Noise		Noise								Start Orbits	
13:12:54								Noise								End Orbits	
13:15:33	Noise							Noise								Start Profile 3 from FL290	
13:17:10	Noise			80		30	125	Noise							11	FL300	
13:18:15	Noise		2	80		45	175	Noise							10	FL310	
13:20:33	Noise			90		35	125	Noise							11	FL320	
13:23:35	Noise		3	20		12	100	Noise							11	FL330	
13:33:31	Noise		4	15		Noise		Noise								FL340	
13:37:28	Noise			5		1	100	Noise							11	End of Profile 3 @ FL350	
13:40:35																Start Run 3.1 @ FL350	
13:41:00	Noise			10		3	100	Noise							11		
13:43:00	Noise		5	20		10	75	Noise							11		
13:45:00	Noise			50		15	125	Noise							10		
13:47:00	Noise			10		10	75	Noise							11		
13:49:00	Noise			20		Noise		Noise									
13:50:49																End of Run 3.1	
13:53:39																Start Run 3.2 @ FL350	
13:54:00	Noise			20		10	75	Noise							11		
13:56:00	Noise			30		15	75	Noise							11		
13:58:00	Noise			80		3	100	Noise							11		
14:00:00	Noise			80		6	50	Noise							11		
14:02:00	Noise		6	150		20	75	Noise							11		
14:03:49																End of Run 3.2	
14:06:49	Noise			20		1		Noise							11	Start Profile 4 from FL350	
14:08:17	Noise			100		25	75	Noise							11	End of Profile 4 & Start Run 4 @ FL340	
14:09:00	Noise			100		30	75	Noise							11		
14:11:00	Noise		7	20		25	75	Noise							11		
14:13:00	Noise			80		25	75	Noise							11		
14:15:00	Noise			10		3	100	Noise							11		
14:17:00	Noise			80		9	75	Noise							11		
14:18:32																End of Run 4	
14:21:41	Noise		8	10		5	75	Noise							11	Start Profile 5 from FL340	
14:22:51	Noise			30		7	125	Noise							11	FL330	
14:24:08	Noise			100		90	150	Noise							11	End of Profile 5 & Start Run 5 @ FL320	
14:26:00	Noise		10	200		150	150	Noise							10		
11:28:00	Noise			15		20	150	Noise							10		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 141

Date: 19/11/05 Operator: MAP DRS time:09:28:00 DAU1 time:09:28:00 DAU2 time: 09:28:00 DAU3 time:09:28:00 AUX1 time:09:28:00 AUX2 time: Page 3 of 3

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:30:00	Noise		10	10		10	100	Noise							11		
11:30:01																End of Run 5	
11:34:56	Noise			20		20	150	Noise							10	Start Profile 6 from FL320	
11:37:17	Noise		11	100		30	175	Noise							10	End of Profile 6 & Start Run 6 @ FL300	
11:38:00	Noise			40		20	150	Noise							10		
11:40:00	Noise			20		6	100	Noise							10		
11:42:00	Noise		12	20		15	150	Noise							10		
11:46:05	Noise			80		10	150	Noise							10	End of Run 6	
11:49:01	Noise			5		8	100	Noise							11	Start Profile 7 from FL 300	
11:50:25	Noise			1												FL290	
14:51:52	Noise			1				Noise								End of Profile 7 & Start Run 7.1 @ FL280	
14:52:00	Noise			1				Noise									
14:54:00	Noise							Noise									
14:56:00	Noise			10				Noise									
14:58:00	Noise							Noise									
14:58:35																End of Run 7.1	
15:02:58																Start Run 7.2 @ FL280	
15:03:00	Noise			10		2	100	Noise							11		
15:05:00	Noise			1				Noise									
15:07:00	Noise							Noise									
15:09:00	Noise							Noise									
15:10:45																End of Run 7.2	
15:11:29																Start Orbits	
15:15:25																End Orbits	
15:17:19	Noise							Noise								Start Profile 8 from FL280	
15:18:34	Noise			10		5	100	Noise							11	FL290	
15:19:46	Noise			10		5	100	Noise							11	FL300	
15:20:46	Noise			100		30	75	Noise							11	FL310	
15:21:51	Noise		13	10		3	75	Noise								End of Profile 8 7 Start Run 8 @ FL320	
15:22:00	Noise			10		10	75	Noise							11		
15:24:00	Noise			5		9	125	Noise							10		
15:26:00	Noise			90		18	100	Noise							10		
15:28:00	Noise			150		18	125	Noise							10		
15:30:00	Noise		15	90		16	125	Noise							10		
15:32:00	Noise		16	80		8	100	Noise							11		
15:34:00	Noise			10		1	75	Noise							11		
15:36:00	Noise			2													
15:38:00	Noise		17	1													
15:38:03																End of Run 8	
	PCASP Flowrate = 1cc/sec																
	PCASP OK at low low altitudes in general with some CH1 noise on occasions but was too noisy at high altitudes																
	2D2-C Sometimes noisy																
	2D2-P Noisy at high altitudes																
	SEADAS time offset = 0																

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B141**Date:** 19/11/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B141_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B141_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B141 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B141_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	21/11/05	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B141 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	21/11/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL19102005.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B141_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B141_mfdX','pmsdata:B141_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	22/11/05	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto complete
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B141_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B141_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	22/11/05	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B141**Date:** 19/11/2005

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B141.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B141.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B141.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B141.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B141_seadas.dat iii) exit	22/11/05	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written Complete, no errors
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B141 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B141_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	22/11/05	Complete, as guideline
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B141 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		This section is optional

a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B141 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	113000 154500 10 PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B141_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		Files on O:\CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B141 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data 0	0	As noted in operator log
e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B141_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkdown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B141_PROC2D	1 113000 154500 0.2 8 2 22/11/05	2D-P continuous noise Note the particle type 2D-C has periodic noise throughout (possibly worse at coldest temperatures). Refer to printed image files for details. Much of this should be rejected during processing but may cause some residual contamination.
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B141_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B141_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	22/11/05	Complete
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B141_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B141_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	22/11/05	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	19/11/05	Flight	B141	log pages
Operator(s)	Ian Rule	Campaign	CAESAR			
Departure	Exeter	Arrival	Exeter			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						
FERA on			at time	0842 ish		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	0842 ish		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	272	Cold	272		
Target heating						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	0842 ish		
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers					
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time	0847 ish	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	271	Cold	271	
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud	1/8 Sc, 1/8 Ci	Precip	nil	
	Surface	frosty	Pressure	1020	
	Other	IAT = 5.7 (sun on rosemount?)			

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	0904	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344	Cold	275
	Deimos:	Hot	332	Cold	280
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	44	30	38	30	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	U/s	30	36	36	39

Power changeover

Headset on before start					
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					
Exit Deimos Software (x)					
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				
Restart Deimos Software					
System running again				at time	

Flight #	B	Date		Operator(s)		log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
0906			Deimos ch 24B very suspicious, MARSS ch16 u/s, ch17 suspicious						
0947			MARSS pc time checked = DRS						
0948			Deimos pc time checked = DRS						
1054			Deimos off for power change						
110621			T/o Exeter						
1111			MARSS ch 16 back, all channels appear to be reacting correctly to climb						
1138 ish			Laptop crashed						
1144			Laptop back, but Demon showing garbage BT's, deimos main prog o/p looks reasonable, MARSS ok so far						
115017	R1	250'	End profile 1, start run						
1153			Restarting Demon and Deimos prog has not brought data back						
120130	R1		End run						
120141	P2	250'	Start profile						
1204			Deimos fully off and on again to try and reset. No luck						
124438	P2	FL290	End profile						
125341	R2	FL290	Start run						
130233	R2	FL290	End run						
130801	O1	FL290	Start orbit, RHD 45 deg, heading 360						
131001			End orbit						
131107	O2	FL290	Start orbit, RHD 45 deg, heading 080						
131256			End orbit						
131535	P3	FL290	Start profile to FL330						
1323			Laptop time check = DRS minus 1 s						
133731	P3	FL350	End profile						
134031	R3.1	FL350	Start run, drop sonde						
135040		FL350	End run						
135358	R3.2	FL350	Start run						
140348			End run						
140648	P4	FL350	Profile down						
140819	P4/R4	FL340	End profile, start run						
1410			Ch16 appears to be dropping out						
			Deimos data starting to reappear on screen, but not making sense, could be error in scan positions.						
141830		FL340	End run						
142141	P5	FL340	Start profile						
142406	P5/R5	FL320	End profile, start run						
143001			End run						
143452	P6	FL320	Start profile						
143716	P6/R6	FL300	End profile, start run						
144605		FL300	End run						
144859	P7		Start profile						
145145	P7/R7.1	FL280	End profile, start run						
145835			End run						
150258	R7.2	FL280	Start run						
151043			End run						

ARIES flight log

Flight: T3141

Location:

page 5 of 6

Date: 19/Nov/05

Operator(s):

Resolution:

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
14 37 28	FL300 ^{R6}	D141H	C	50.8	12.7	-30.2	-189.9	16.8	CH1	↑ — 00 —
14 38 34		I	O	50.4	12.5	-29.9	-190.6	17.1	Z1 x 2	
14 40 35		J	C	51.3	11.8	-30.2	"	10.6	CH1 x 1	
14 41 46		K	O	50.6	12.9	-29.8	-191.2	12.6	Z1 x 2	
14 43 56		L	C	51.5	12.6	-29.7		8.7	CH1 x 1	
14 45 04		M	O	51.2	12.5	-29		11.5	Z1 x 1	
14 46 19		N	C	51.3	12.4	-29	-189.9	9.6	CH1 x 1	
14 48 59	P7 ↓									
14 51 41	FL280 R7-1	O	C	51	12	-27	-191.2	17	CH1 x 1	
14 53		P	O	50	12	-27	-190.6	17	Z1 x F3	Shutter open a little late
14 55 46		Q	C	50.7	12.5	-27.8	"	9.1	CH1 x 1	
14 56 59		R	O	50.9	12.4	-27.2	"	11.6	Z1 x 1	Shutter late
14 58 06		S	O	51.1	12.6	-27.1		9.4	Z1 x 1	Back of ear.
14 59 09	FL280	T	C	50.9	12.4	-27.0		8.0	CH1 x 1	
15 03 05	R7.2	U	C	50.9	11.8	-25.9		15.6	CH1 x 1	
15 04 13		V	O	51.1	12.4	-25		16.4	Z1 x 3	
15 07 04		W	C	51.2	11.7	-25.7	-190.6	9.5	CH1	
15 08 14		X	O	50.6	12.3	-25.8	"	11.9	Z1 x 2	
15 10 14		Y	C	51.3	12.5			9.4	CH1	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B4-1	Date	19/11/2005	Operator(s)	M. GLEW	log page	1 of 2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

1055						Time synchronised, T +13°C, only running petrie?
1108						shutters don't always go to open/shut automatically. run 2 dark current
						playing around. Camera shows det picked up during take off (SWS pointing off at take off) Time set at 11:47Z, error - 37ms
1148	P1	800'	180	1000	1000	
115017	R1	250'	180	1000	1000	T +13°C
1155						dark current
1201						dark current
120130	R1 end	250'	180	1000	1000	Timer reset error - 88ms
120500	P2	FL257	0	350	1000	Little NIR signal.
1207						Looked forward to check NIR working - strong signal from looking at aircraft.
1218						Looked forward - strong signal from aircraft.
1225						Dark current.
1226	P2	FL200'	0	350	1000	Some NIR SIGNAL
1235	P2	FL2107'	0	200	500	stronger signals 1238 Time reset error 48ms
124438	P2 END	FL290	0	350	500	
1247		FL290	6F	350	500	Aircraft pitch 5-5
125341	R2	FL290	6F	350	500	
1257	R2	FL290	6F	100	200	
1259	R2	FL290	6F	200	200	1300 T +15°C
130235	R2 end	FL290	6F	200	200	
130801	O1	FL290	6F	100	200	R14 4T° No clipping, good max
131107	O2	FL290	6F	100	200	1310 Time reset error - 74ms
131256	O2 end.					Pitch 4.5° in orbit
132500	P3	FL320	180	350	500	T +15°C Timer reset error 50ms
133741	P3 END	FL350	180	250	500	
134031	R3.1	FL350	180	250	500	
1346	CAN SEE	LOW CLOUD PRODUCING HIGH COUNTS				
13538	R3.2	FL350	6F	250	500	
135700	R3.2	FL350	6F	500	500	LOW NIR SIGNAL
140819	R4	FL340	6F	500	500	T +16°C 14:00
141830	R4 END					1404 Time reset error 2ms
142406	R5	FL320	6F	500	500	1423 Time reset error 100ms
1426	R5	FL320	6F	350	500	VIS was saturating at 500ms
143001	R5 END					
143716	R6	FL300	6F	350	500	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 141

Date: 19th November 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JO1D	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JO1D	N	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	Y		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	Y
CO	N	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B141

Date: 19th November 2005

Instruments

1. INU – No response from the serial link initially on the pre-flight. Reset INU, no difference. Reset INU and CBs, then okay.
2. TWC – not fitted
3. HORACE – FWVS raw data reading 65535. Log file shows “timeout or incomplete data”. Data looks okay on FWVS pc.
4. HORACE – CPC display and raw data reading 0. Reset CPC at 12:52, no change.
5. Upper camera window – needs to be cleaned.
6. Printer – not printing out map plot from aft Core Console pcs, only bands of lines

Other Instruments' status

AVAPS – 2 Sondes launched, no problems

ARIES, SWS, MARSS, ADA, CPI, FWVS – Okay

DEIMOS – slightly suspect, need to check data

Cloud Physics – Okay except 2D-P & PCASP at high altitude

TAFTS – No long-wave data

Aircraft

1. De-Ice wings and tail pre-flight.
2. Wash-hand basin – cold tap button snapped off. (Water frozen for much of flight)

Satcom H Calls –

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B141:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
TAFTS	No log is ever taken for TAFTS
ADA/CPI	No log taken or no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647
Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk